

DIRECTIONS FOR THE EFFECTIVE USE OF DEBT FUNDS IN THE FINANCIAL ACTIVITIES OF ELECTRIC POWER NETWORK ENTERPRISES

O.U. Mavlonov

PhD, independent researcher Regional Electric Networks JSC

ORCID:0009-0009-7463-3795

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19630549>

Abstract. *This article examines the effective use of debt in the financial activities of electric power grid enterprises using the example of JSC “Regional Electric Grids”. The study evaluates the impact of debt burden, leverage, liquidity and profitability indicators on the financial stability of the enterprise using econometric methods. In particular, the relationship between EBIT, ROE and ROA indicators and debt was analyzed using regression and VAR models. The results showed that an increase in the debt share negatively affects profitability indicators, and maintaining debt at an optimal level is an important factor in ensuring financial stability. At the end of the study, conclusions were drawn on improving debt management in electric power grid enterprises, effective tariff policy, and the gradual introduction of market mechanisms.*

Keywords: *electric grid company, financial stability, debt, leverage, profitability, ROE, ROA*

Introduction. The financial stability of each enterprise is of great importance for its long-term and sustainable development. Although the financial and economic activities of state-owned enterprises differ from those of private sector enterprises, their main goal is to achieve sustainable growth. Ensuring the financial stability of state-owned enterprises directly affects the economic situation of the country. The financial crises of such state-owned enterprises can require significant budgetary funds from the state budget. It can also negatively affect the standard of living of the population and the activities of production enterprises through service and supply disruptions. Unsatisfied financial stability of power grid enterprises can lead to an increase in electricity prices and can cause non-monetary factors to increase prices in the economy. For this reason, the development of directions for ensuring the financial stability of power grid enterprises is becoming increasingly important in achieving the set goals of the country's economy.

Literature review. The OECD (2015) report highlights that the capital structure of state-owned enterprises is often formed in a manner that is constrained by market mechanisms. As a result, high debt burdens and low profitability negatively affect financial stability. The OECD justifies the need to form an optimal ratio between capital and debt in state-owned enterprises. According to the “soft budget constraint” theory developed by János Kornai (1986), state-owned enterprises often operate without the risk of bankruptcy, as they are supported by the government. This leads to excessive debt accumulation and a decrease in financial discipline.

The International Monetary Fund (2020) studies assess the debt of state-owned enterprises as a source of hidden fiscal risks. The report notes that debt under state guarantees can threaten the sustainability of the state budget.

According to the World Bank (2014) report, the efficiency of capital use in state-owned enterprises largely depends on the quality of corporate governance. SOEs with a high level of transparency and accountability have a high return on capital.

The classical capital structure theory of Modigliani Franco and Merton Miller (1958) discusses the impact of the ratio of debt to equity on the value of the enterprise. Although this theory is based on perfect market conditions, it also serves as an important theoretical framework for SOEs. According to the Asian Development Bank (2019) study, if leverage (debt level) is high in state-owned enterprises, financial stability decreases, but when properly managed, debt can stimulate investment growth.

The International Energy Agency (2021) report notes that debt instruments are widely used in state-owned energy enterprises due to the large capital requirements, but this increases financial risks.

Methodology. Econometric analysis was carried out on a number of financial indicators of the financial and economic activities of JSC "Regional Electric Networks". These analyses were carried out based on econometric models and hypotheses studied by scientists. The main focus was on studying the dependence of other relative indicators on the profitability indicators of the joint-stock company. The forecast value of the financial indicator of the joint-stock company was calculated. The VAR model was used to calculate this forecast indicator. Also, the MAPE (Mean Absolute Percentage Error) test was conducted on the reliability of the forecast indicators.

Econometric analysis was carried out on the basis of the relative indicators obtained from the financial and balance sheet reports of the JSC "Regional Electric Networks". In it, the leverage indicator as the main influencing factors and the profitability of capital and assets as a result of the financial activities of the enterprise were taken as the dependent variable for the analysis.

As a general overview of the model used, we can highlight the following:

$$Y = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \mu$$

$$Y = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 X_t + \beta_2 X_{t-1} + \beta_3 X_{t-3} + \dots + \beta_n X_{t-n} + \mu$$

$$Y = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \mu$$

each loan is an expense that reduces future profits for enterprises. For this reason, a linear regression analysis was carried out to determine the impact of the previous year's value of the loan on the profitability indicators of the current period. The calculations according to this regression model are carried out based on the formula in the books and can be calculated as the maximum limit value for the amount of profit to be obtained from model.

Analysis and results. According to the regression analysis, a 1% increase in the leverage ratio on short-term liabilities causes an 8% decrease in EBIT. A 1% increase in the leverage ratio on total liabilities causes an increase in EBIT by approximately 11%. In this case, the factor that causes a change in the real value of the amount of debt is inflation.

Table 1. Results of regression econometric analysis

T	LnEBI	t-value		p		[95% Conf Interval]	Sig	
	Coef.	St.Err.	-value					
	LnLev1	-	3.	.	.	-	-	
		8.343	014	2.77	012	14.65	2.035	*
	lnLev2	10	4.	:	.	1.73	20	
		.904	382	.49	022	3	.075	*
	Consta	-	3.	.	.	-	6.	

Table-3. Results of linear regression analysis

ROE		Coef.	St.Err.	t- value	p- value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
lev1		-	.0	-	.	-	-	
		.027	09	2.89	009	.046	.008	**
Consta		10	1.		0	10	10	
nt		3.016	233	3.56		0.445	5.588	**
Mean			100.062		SD dependent		3.764	
dependent var					var			
R-squared			0.295		Number of		22	
					obs			
F-test			8.369		Prob > F		0.009	
Akaike	crit.		116.046		Bayesian crit.		118.228	
(AIC)					(BIC)			

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

ROE		Coef.	St.Err.	t- value	p- value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
lev2		-	.0	-	.	-	-	
		.098	44	2.26	035	.189	.007	*
Consta		10	2.		0	10	10	
nt		4.294	014	1.78		0.093	8.495	**
Mean			100.062		SD dependent		3.764	
dependent var					var			
R-squared			0.203		Number of		22	
					obs			
F-test			5.092		Prob > F		0.035	
Akaike	crit.		118.746		Bayesian crit.		120.928	
(AIC)					(BIC)			

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

We can obtain the following data on the analysis of the impact of leverage indicators on return on capital. In this case, we can see that a 1 percent change in debt funds relative to the company's own funds leads to a decrease in the profitability indicator by -0.027 percent.

We can also see from the regression model that a 1 percent change in debt funds relative to total assets causes a decrease in the profitability of the enterprise by 0.098 percent. Also, according to the study, it was found that there is no regression relationship between the liquidity of the joint-stock company and the profitability indicator. Also, the regression relationships with the profitability indicator of the assets taken for the study are analyzed.

Table 4. Linear regression analysis results

ROA		Coef.	St.Err.	t- value	p- value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
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	lev1	-	.0	-	.	-	-	
		.01	04	2.70	014	.018	.002	*
	Consta	10	.5	:	0	10	10	
nt		1.437	08	99.6		0.377	2.497	**

Mean		100.300		SD dependent		1.522	
dependent var				var			
R-squared		0.267		Number of		22	
				obs			
F-test		7.297		Prob > F		0.014	
Akaike crit.		77.037		Bayesian crit.		79.219	
(AIC)				(BIC)			

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

ROA							
		Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf Interval]	Sig
	lev2	-	.0	-	.	-	-
		.038	18	2.15	044	.075	.001
	Consta	10	.8	:	0	10	10
nt		1.948	22	24.1		0.234	3.662

Mean		100.300		SD dependent		1.522	
dependent var				var			
R-squared		0.188		Number of		22	
				obs			
F-test		4.640		Prob > F		0.044	
Akaike crit.		79.289		Bayesian crit.		81.472	
(AIC)				(BIC)			

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

ROA							
		Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf Interval]	Sig
	Liq	-	.0	-	.	-	0
		.019	09	2.06	053	.038	
	Consta	10	.8	:	0	10	10
nt		1.961	62	18.2		0.162	3.76

Mean		100.300		SD dependent		1.522	
dependent var				var			
R-squared		0.175		Number of		22	
				obs			
F-test		4.229		Prob > F		0.053	
Akaike crit.		79.659		Bayesian crit.		81.841	

(AIC)

(BIC)

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

The results of the regression analysis of these leverage indicators on the return on assets indicators show that a change in leverage indicators by 1 unit can lead to a decrease in the profitability indicator by -0.01 percent and a decrease in the profitability indicator by -0.038 percent. A change in the liquidity indicator by the same amount causes a decrease in the profitability indicator by -0.019 percent.

Based on the results of the research, we can conclude that short-term debt serves to form the working capital of the enterprise and it is emphasized that it is possible to increase profits through effective management of short-term debt.

That is, it can be more effective than long-term debt, but long-term debt is attracted to finance newly established enterprises and their strategic goals. Also

According to the regression result, the formed regression model looks like this:

$$Y = 97.246 + 0.36 \text{ lev}^2 - 0.006 \text{ Lev}^2 + e$$

Without the influence of the change in the leverage ratio, the profitability index due to the change in other factors is 97.246 percent. Also, by calculating the derivative value of this model, the share of debt funds in total assets is found.

That is, the leverage value is equal to the calculated value of $0.36 - 0.012 \text{ lev}^2 = 0$. Also, according to the result, it is shown that the share of total debt in total assets should not exceed 30 percent. In the analysis of the statistical significance of the model according to this indicator, we can see that the model residuals are correctly distributed according to the Shapiro-Wilk W test, the Shapiro-Wilk W test $\text{Prob} > z$ is equal to 0.147, and we can conclude that the model residuals are correctly distributed and that the model is statistically significant.

Also, according to the model results, we find the forecast values of the profitability indicator using the VAR model (Vector Autoregressive model). This model allows us to predict the values of future variables in time series. That is, it forecasts taking into account the time factor and the number of lags. The forecast indicators of assets and profitability indicators are presented according to the results of the econometric model, the value of which is transferred.

Table 5. Forecast values (%) of ROE and ROA indicators of the Regional Electricity Networks Enterprise Aj according to the VAR model

T	ROA (p)	ROA (o)	ROE (p)	ROE(o)
2025q1	99,8	102,92	98,72	106,3
2025q2	99,98	103,15	99,13	106,9
2025q3	100,09	103,31	99,44	107,4
2025q4	100,14	103,35	99,6	107,6
2026q1	100,17	103,37	99,7	107,65
2026q2	100,19	103,38	99,7	107,7
2026q3	100,19	103,39	99,77	107,7
2026q4	100,19	103,39	99,79	107,7

Tests were conducted on these forecast indicators. The reliability of the test results was also positive with an error of 5%. It was also predicted that the profitability indicators of the enterprise for the next quarters would show positive results.

Conclusion. As a result of our research, we were able to develop the following scientific conclusions and proposals: we believe that it is necessary to carry out these influencing factors in connection with the financial and economic activities of the enterprise by dividing them into financial and non-financial factors. We can conclude that the financial relative indicators of the state-owned regional power grid enterprise are not stable.

According to current calculations, the Altman model predicts that the enterprise is in financial difficulty and may encounter financial problems. Also, the analysis of debt and equity relations in the financial activities of the joint-stock company shows an increase in the share of debt. At the same time, maintaining debts at effective and marginal levels, in turn, serves the stability of the enterprise.

The determination of electricity prices by the higher authorities of the Electric Network Enterprise JSC and the existence of prices classified by price, in turn, negatively affects the low level of income and profitability indicators presented as relative indicators.

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